

Dimensions and Characteristics of Organizational Behavior: Impact and Competitive Advantage

Dr. J. Jose Prabhu

Research Associate and Visiting Professor, Management and Engineering College, Tamil Nadu, India

ABSTRACT

The study of organizational behavior gives insight into how staff members behave and perform in the work environment. It helps us develop an understanding of the facets that can motivate staff members, enhance their efficiency, and help organizations establish a solid and also trusting relationship with their staff members. Human actions are inherent in each person which indicates his features, his way of behaving as well as assuming are his very own attributes while business actions are a group or company society special of each very own felt and also done. The study of Organizational Behavior (OB) is really intriguing as well as challenging too. It is related to individuals, a team of individuals collaborating in teams. The research ends up being a lot more challenging when situational factors connect. The research of organizational behavior connects to the expected behavior of an individual in the organization. No two individuals are likely to behave in the same manner in a certain work circumstance. It is the predictability of a supervisor concerning the expected behavior of an individual. There are no absolutes in human behavior. It is the human variable that is contributing to the performance hence the study of human practices is very important. Great value consequently must be affixed to the study.

KEYWORDS: Organizational behavior, Human behavior, Dimensions of OB, Characteristics of organizational behavior

I. INTRODUCTION

"Organizational behavior is a part of administration tasks worried about understanding, anticipating and affecting specific practices in an organisational setting."-- Callahan, Fleenor and also Kudson.

"Organizational behavior is a branch of the Social Sciences that seeks to build theories that can be applied" to predicting, understanding as well as managing practices in work organisations."-- Raman J. Aldag.

"Organisational practices is the research and application of expertise regarding just how people act within an organisation. It is a human device for human benefit. It applies broadly to the practices of individuals in all types of organisation."-- Newstrom as well as Davis.

"Organisational behavior is straight worried about the understanding, production as well as control of human behaviour in organisations."-- Fred Luthans.

"Organisational behavior is a discipline that investigates the effect that people, groups and also framework carry behavior within the organisations for the function of using such understanding towards improving an organization's performance."-- Stephens P. Robbins

Scientists, management specialists, psychologists, and also social scientists need to comprehend the real credentials of an individual, his history, social framework, academic upgrade, the effect of social teams as well as various other

How to cite this paper: Dr. J. Jose Prabhu "Dimensions and Characteristics of Organizational Behavior: Impact and Competitive Advantage" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-4 | Issue-3, April 2020, pp.671-676, URL: www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd30632.pdf

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situational aspects on behavior. Managers under whom a person is functioning ought to be able to clarify, anticipate, review as well as change human behavior that will largely rely on the expertise, skill and experience of the manager in managing large groups of people in diverse circumstances. Preemptive activities need to be considered human behavior projecting. The worth system, emotional knowledge, organizational culture, task layout and also the work environment are very important causal agents in figuring out human practices. Domino effect partnership plays an important duty in how a person is most likely to behave in a specific circumstance as well as its impact on performance. An ideal organizational society can modify private practices. Recent patterns exist in laying higher tension on organizational advancement and also drinking a favorable organizational society in each individual. It additionally includes cultivating a team spirit and inspiration to ensure that the business purposes are attained. There is a demand for a commitment on the part of the administration that ought to be continuous and also incremental in nature.

The field of the business behavior does not rely on reductions based on sixth sense but attempts to gather info relating to a problem in a clinical fashion under controlled problems. It uses info and analyzes the findings so that the practices of a specific and group can be canalized as wanted. A lot of psychotherapists, social scientists and academicians have accomplished a study on various concerns related to company practices. Worker efficiency and also job satisfaction are components of the accomplishment of

individual and organizational objectives. Organizations have been set up to fulfill the demands of the people. In today's affordable globe, companies need to be growth-oriented. This is possible when performance is made certain relative to the quantity of the item to be created with absolutely no mistake of high quality. Worker absence, as well as turnover, has an adverse impact on productivity. An employee who absents frequently can not contribute towards productivity as well as the development of the company. Similarly, worker turnover triggers boosted the price of manufacturing. Work contentment is a major aspect to evaluate the performance of a specific in the direction of his job. Pleased employees are efficient workers who contribute in the direction of constructing a suitable job culture in a company. Organizations are made up of a number of individuals working individually or jointly in groups, and also a variety of such teams makes a division and also a variety of such departments make a company. It is an official framework and all divisions need to work in a work with fashion to accomplish the business objective. It is as a result essential for all employees to have a favorable attitude in the direction of work. They need to work in the kindly ambiance as well as achieve appointed goals. It is additionally important for managers to develop appropriate work culture. Use of authority, a delegation of particular powers to staff, department of labor, reliable interaction, benchmarking, re-engineering, job re-design and also empowerment are several of the vital variables to make sure that an organization can work as a well-product maker. This is not just suitable for manufacturing organizations but likewise to the solution and also social companies.

II. Literature Review:

Connolly, T., et al (1997) examined about the adverse effect connected with bad choice outcomes is typically believed to include sensations of sorrow or self-blame. For example, studies revealing better remorse related to active than with passive options are interpreted as the active chooser stacking self-recrimination on the top the frustration of a poor result. Matching rejoicing is proposed for active selection that leads to good results. The five experiments reported right here obstacle such a view. In each, theoretical individuals experienced similar gains or losses, some as an outcome of their own choice, others as a result of an exterior, approximate process. Through examinations of last outcomes were heavily affected by the courses through which the results were gotten to, as well as by the contrast levels that were evoked, in no instance was choice agency a significant impact. In these experiments, then, the "active chooser" effect appears, even more, a matter of modification than of selection, of the path taken instead of whether one is the motorist or the traveler. Additional research will be required to establish the situations under which various prominent contrasts are stimulated.

Gelfand, M. J., et al (2007) examined about this short article examines a study on cross-cultural organizational behavior (OB). After a quick review of the background of cross-cultural OB, we review research on work motivation, or the elements that stimulate, direct, and also maintain initiative across societies. We next take into consideration the connection between the species as well as the organization, and review study on society and organizational dedication, mental contracts, justice, citizenship behavior, as well as person-environment fit. Afterward, we consider exactly how

individuals manage their connection in organizations, and review research study on society and arrangement as well as disputing, teams, and management, complied with by research study on handling throughout borders as well as expatriation. The evaluation shows that developmentally, cross-cultural research in OB is maturing. Yet we likewise highlight critical obstacles for a future research study, including moving beyond values to discuss social distinctions, attending to degrees of evaluation issues, including social and also business context elements right into cross-cultural research, taking indigenous perspectives seriously, and moving past intracultural contrasts to understand the characteristics of cross-cultural interfaces.

Johns, G. (2006) studied about the influence of context on organizational actions is not sufficiently acknowledged or valued by researchers. he define context as situational opportunities and restraints that influence the incident and definition of business habits as well as useful partnerships between variables, and he propose 2 degrees of evaluation for considering context-- one based in journalistic practice as well as the other in traditional social psychology. A number of means of contextualizing research study are thought about.

III. Analysis of Organizational behavior and Organization's Structure:

Miner, J. B. (2005) Organizational behavior in the analysis of an organization's structure, functions, and the behavior of its individuals. The behavioral study includes both teams along with people. It is an inter-disciplinary area as well as has its origins in sociology and also psychology. Organizational behavior is based on sociology, as words organization itself stands for social collectivity.

Miner, J. B. (2003) It is linked to psychology since the subject includes the research study of people, individually as well as in groups in the work environment (essentially, an organization). Person and also group behavior is again the feature of lots of variables, which encompass other interdisciplinary areas such as business economics, government, social anthropology, engineering, and also personnel administration. The scope of business behaviour is consequently considerable. A company requires to handle all these elements so that it can sustain itself in an open market.

Figure 1: Organizational behavior structures for Individuals and Groups

Miner, J. B. (2002) theoretically, it is difficult for us to draw a line between management as well as business practices. It can be claimed that one supplements the various other. Some business behaviour issues have their origins in administration procedures. As a matter of fact, the research study of administration started much before the research of organizational behavior.

Research studies in business behaviour began in the middle of the twentieth century. Business behavior researches, therefore, attract from monitoring theories to comprehend elements such as business structure, the behavior of individuals in a company, and the issues worrying outside and inner fit.

Pinder, C. C., & Moore, L. F. (1980) Effective administration of business practices mostly relies on the monitoring practices that prevail in an organization. Understanding business behavior, consequently, needs a clear understanding of the basics of monitoring.

Going back in history, we discover that prior to the industrial transformation (which took place in Europe in the middle of the eighteenth century), individuals made use of to manage their very own financial activity with home-centered production systems. They themselves were the proprietors of work, services, and also funding. Because involvement was spontaneous (as it was their own job) and also the dimension of tasks was tiny (constrained to the family members) monitoring as a significant human task did not get much acknowledgment in those days.

Lee, C., & Earley, P. C. (1992) with the innovation of innovation, interaction, and transport, the domain name of the marketplace expanded past the adjoining locations. It went to this point of time that arranged manufacturing activity in the form of factory-centered production systems began to arise.

People began operating in teams to achieve common goals. It was not feasible for individuals or private families to achieve these goals. An understanding of management and also organizational practices then became crucial for coordinating the efforts of individuals operating in groups. With boosting global competitors as well as constant advancements in innovation, the job of managers is becoming increasingly more essential.

IV. Two fundamental Components of Organizational behavior:

1. The nature of the man.
2. The nature of the organization.

Bateman, T. S., & Crant, J. M. (1993) To put it simply, organizational behavioral may be the organization of an individual's practices in regard to physical means and also resources so as to attain the wanted objective of the organization.

V. Organisational Behaviour, Organisational Theory, Organisational Psychology and Human Resource Management:

O'Neil, S., & Koekemoer, E. (2016) Organizational behavior is usually confused with the organisational concept, organisational psychology, and also human resource

management. Organisational psychology restricts itself to psychological variables only whereas organisational behaviour thinks about and also incorporates all the branches of study e.g. Science, modern technology, economics, sociology, psychology and so forth and so forth.

Figure 2: Organizational Environment Structures

Schaper, N. (2004) Organisational behaviour is the basis of personnel management and growth. The former is concept oriented whereas the latter is worried about the modern technology of human growth. The variables influencing human advancement are clinically studied under organisational practices.

Cascio, W. F., & Aguinis, H. (2005) Personnel management, is turned on, routed and also channelized by the application of the expertise of organisational behavior which has actually ended up being a discipline, study and application for the advancement of human resources as well as the organisation overall. Hence, we can claim that all these terms are related yet not identified with each various other.

VI. Characteristics of Organizational Behavior:

1. Behavioral Strategy to Monitoring:

Cohen, A., & Avrahami, A. (2006) Organisational behavior is that component of entire management which stands for the behavioural technique to administration. Organizational practices have actually emerged as a distinct field of study due to the value of human behavior in organisations.

2. Cause and Effect Connection:

Van Dam, K., et al (2008) Human behavior is typically taken in terms of domino effect connection as well as not in philosophical terms. It helps in forecasting the practices of people. It offers generalizations that supervisors can make use of to anticipate the impact of certain tasks on human practices.

3. Organisational Behaviour is a Branch of Social Sciences:

Organisational behaviors are heavily influenced by numerous various other social sciences viz. psychology, sociology as well as sociology. It draws a rich range of research from these disciplines.

4. Three Degrees of Analysis:

O'Driscoll, M. P. (1987) Organisational behaviour encompasses the study of three degrees of analysis namely specific behavior, inter-individual behaviour and also the practices of organisations themselves. The field of organisational behaviour accepts all these degrees as being corresponding per various other.

5. Scientific research along with an Art:

Omerzel, D. G. (2016) Organizational behavior is scientific research along with an art. The methodical expertise about human behaviour is a science and the application of behavioural expertise and abilities is an art. Organisational behaviour is not a specific science because it can not precisely anticipate the behavior of individuals in organisations. At the finest, a manager can generalize to a restricted degree and oftentimes, he needs to act upon the basis of partial information.

6. A Body of Concept, Research and Application:

Suman, S., & Srivastava, A. K. (2012) Organisational behaviour contains a body of theory, research and application which aids in recognizing the human practices in the organisation. All these methods help the managers to solve human issues in organisations.

7. Beneficial to both Organisation as well as People:

Rowe, G., & Wright, G. (1996) Organisational behaviour produces an ambiance where both organisation and also people are profited by each other. An affordable climate is created to make sure that workers may get much-required contentment and the organisation might attain its purposes.

8. Reasonable Thinking:

Gaddis, B. H., & Foster, J. L. (2015) Organisational behaviour offers logical reasoning about people as well as their behaviour. The major objective of organizational behaviour is to discuss and also anticipate human behaviour in organisations, to ensure that result generating circumstances can be created.

VII. Nature of Organizational Behavior:

Sundin, L., et al (2006) Organisational habits in the research study of human practices in the organisations. Whenever a specific sign up with an organisation he brings with him a one-of-a-kind collection of individual qualities, experiences from various other organisations as well as an individual history. At the first stage organisational behavior need to look at the distinct perspective that each specific offers the work setting.

Kipkebut, D. J. (2013) The 2nd stage of organisational practices is to examine the characteristics of how the incoming individuals engage with the wider organisation. No individual can operate in seclusion. He enters into contact with other individuals and also the organisation in a variety of methods. The individual who signs up with a new organisation has to enter into call with the associates, managers, formal plans and procedures of the organisation etc.

Over the time, he is affected by his job experience and the organisation along with his individual experiences and also maturation. On the other hand, the organisation is also affected by the existence or lack of a person. Thus, it is

essential that OB should examine the ways in which the individuals and also organisation communicate with each various other.

The organisational practices need to be examined from the point of view of the organisation itself due to the fact that an organisation exists prior to a particular specific participates in and also continues to exist after she or he has left the organisation. Thus, OB is the study of human behavior in the organisation, the individual-organisation communication and also the organisation itself. And these aspects are affected by the outside setting in which the individuals, as well as the organisation, exist.

Georgalis, J., et al (2015) Thus, we can claim that we cannot research private behavior completely without learning something about the organisation. On the other hand, we cannot examine the organisations without examining the behavior of the individuals operating in it. This is since the organisation influences and is affected by the people operating in it. Furthermore, both the individuals and the organisation are affected by the external environment. Hence, the field of organisational behaviour is a complicated field. It looks for to throw light on the whole canvas of humans consider the organisations which will certainly consist of the domino effects of such behaviour.

VIII. Influence of Personality on Organizational Behavior

Nga, J. K. H., & Shamuganathan, G. (2010) examined about to recognize business behavior, it is vital to recognize private behaviour. The nature and personality of private human beings is the root cause of the behavior. Words' personality is derived from the Latin word identity. It signifies the masks that made use of to be worn by staged gamers in old Greek dramatization.

For this reason, the character is the superficial social image that we adopt. Additionally, we can also check out personality as a representation of the most dominant features in the behavior of a person that are observable (specifically, aggression or shyness). It is with an individuality that a specific make a total perception on others in various social setups.

Halder, S., Roy, A., & Chakraborty, P. K. (2017) A quick comparison of behavior, character, as well as personality, can be made by attributing practices as the outside appearance as well as not the exposition of true feelings of the mind. The character is the index of the mind and feelings, that is, behavior that is supported as well as guided by the mind, while the character on the other hand, is self-directed behaviour. Personality parts, therefore, are the mind (clearness as well as understanding), the will (solidity and also equality), the heart (conservation, heat, expansiveness, and also magnetism), vigor (power), and also the physique (willpower and also endurance for the job).

Sikalieh, D., & Mkoji, D. (2012) Individuality is the research of the individual, that is, the complete human person. In business behavior researches, the specific character is necessary because the staff members' specific personalities describe their dynamic mental frameworks and also worked with procedures of the mind, which identify their psychological and also behavioural changes to the company.

Character is dynamic since mental structures of individual employees continuously establish over their lifetime. Additionally, in organizational behavior studies, the individuality, as well as the private behavioral pattern of the staff members, come to be a vital construct to change as well as do well in work circumstances.

Jafri, H. (2014) specifically in a transforming organization setting, to get the best fit, employers take advantage of individuality tests in choice and recruitment decisions. This apart, the rate of interest in character evaluation is also crucial for social transformation in an organization. With the understanding of cognitive and psychological bases of human behaviour, individuality analysis has obtained additionally significance.

In the above backdrop, individuality research studies are really concentrating on personality differences- types and also characteristics, and so on that is, a few of the qualities of individuals that can vary from each various other. Despite the fact that commonly we take into consideration these from the emotional point of view, to comprehend them holistically calls for factor to consider of biology (with even more focus on neurology), development as well as genes, experience as well as assumption, inspiration as well as feeling, finding out and also memory, developing psychology, psychopathology, psychotherapy, and so on. There are different individuality concepts, yet there is no unified method.

IX. Personality and Organizational Behaviour:

Miller, R. L., Griffin, M. A., & Hart, P. M. (1999) Organizational behavior of people in an organization originates from both ecological in addition to private aspects. From the environmental strategy, social, group, as well as social impacts and also individual components prolong throughout cognitive capacities, obtained expertise, personality designs, inspiration, and also physical qualities.

A typical facet of individuality is the way in which we consider its result on actions. We have a tendency to consider this in regards to a person with a specific collection of qualities. As an instance, we consider an aggressive, uneasy individual as one more than likely to act in a hostile means.

Robertson, I., & Callinan, M. (1998) the instructions of the link are thought to stem from personality type and also transfer to actions. That is to state, your originality substantially influences specifically how you act, not the other way around-- that your actions would clarify your character.

As an example, we normally assume that a hesitant individual is not more than likely to head to celebrations, yet we might additionally think that somebody that does not probably to parties or various other affairs is more than likely to end up being reluctant. The assumed collaboration between personality as well as also job-related techniques is amongst the crucial reasons that it is of interest to those that study as well as likewise handle companies.

Among the fundamental problems in the understanding of people's techniques is specifically just how we comprehend the individual in a business arrangement. Jackson and also

Carter (2000) mentioned that in task companies, we usually take a limited sight of the individual, concentrating a lot much more on the level of determination (or otherwise) to pursue business goals.

Yet our experience discloses that in work companies, individuals are additional complex in their behavioral patterns. In organizational contexts, we can account for such difficult behavior disorders from social as well as additionally psychological perspectives. For instance, we can consider people in the context of task, identification, personality, or self.

X. Conclusion:

Various ideas as well as designs in the area of organizational behavior effort to recognize, not only the human practices but additionally change their attitude and also promote skills to ensure that they can act better. This is done medically; consequently, the business behavior field is a scientific discipline. It has actually been observed that we usually form our viewpoint based upon the symptoms of a concern as well as do not really go to the source of the occurring. Scientific research of organizational practices is used in nature. Disciplines like psychology, sociology and also political science have added in regards to numerous researches and also concepts to the area of organizational practices. A leader needs to be able to communicate with his junior and maintain them in picture as to the happenings in the organization. Individuals promote a business culture for mutual advantage. National politics is often made use of to develop dispute with the objective of expanding the self-power base to the damaging of organizational development. National politics, in Indian context has actually made inroads based upon faith, caste system in the choice making procedure which has actually brought about formation of informal groups in the organization that commonly make use of the company for fulfillment of personal goals at the cost of business goals. Dispute and also controlling power bases require to be taken care of in a proper manner to modify human behavior and promote different people in the direction of achieving greater efficiency. Power characteristics play a considerable duty in organization situations in various setting.

XI. References:

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